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The Effect of Technological Innovation on Free, Fair and Credible Election in Nigeria: A Case Study of Ethiope West Local Government Area of Delta State.

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ABSTRACT

The current practice of electing people into offices through fraudulent means necessitate the introduction of technological device such as the permanent voters' card and BVAS in Nigeria. However, the inability of the electoral umpire to improve election outcomes through these technologies and consolidate democratic trust raised a lot of doubt as to whether Nigeria and Ethiope West Local Government is ripe for electoral technology. Accordingly, the hypothesis tested by the study is mainly that technology innovations have no significant positive effect on free, fair and credible elections in Nigeria. The paper used the recently concluded 2023 general election in Nigeria and seeks to provide empirical indications. The study used primary data collected through questionnaires while logistic regression was employed for the analysis. It was found by the study that the deployment of technology for voter registration boosts the acceptability of election outcomes, as people can now access and verify the voters' register. Also, the transparency provided by technology, such as the BVAS increased people's confidence in the electoral system and its outcomes. However, the study found that despite the deployment of BVAS, underaged voting and over voting were very prominent most especially in the northern part of Nigeria in the 2023 general elections leading to disaffections among contestants. The paper recommended the need to use technological device to block loopholes that negate credible elections and culture of impunities in electoral system in Nigeria.

Keywords: Technology device, Card Reader, Ethiope West L.G.A.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of technology in the conduct of elections has stirred heated debate from scholars, policy makers and the public in Africa in general and Nigeria in particular. In typical democratic setting, election is the best government one needs to practices to change the behavior of rulership position periodically and this democratic governance does not only promote leadership quality but also encourages accountability. Democracy allows massive participation and helps to retain power in the hands of the people. Those

whose responsibility is to exercise political authorities in a society perform it with the explicit consent and genuine mandate expressed at periodic intervals by the electorates through an open, free and fair electoral process (Ojie, 2006; Omoleke, 2017). This means that democracy must be a system of government where the people chose and elect their leaders to govern them. Lijphart *et al.*, (2007) averred that the emergence of a series of technological innovations like cyber-citizenship, e-politics, and web-democracy, among others, encouraged the development and deployment of electronic information processing networks, to help shape and determine the political environment all over the world.

In the late 1800s, a set of electoral technologies invaded the electoral space to bring about new political representation, as standardized and government-issued electronic ballots were deployed together, with voting machines, to create a free and fair election (Anderson & Kreiss, 2013). These narratives were said to have informed the projection aimed at developing an online voting system, an e-poll project that enabled voters to be identified according to their voting site via fingerprint recognition sensor system, touch-screen electronic device, server technology to absorb and manage traffic data generated by electoral population, bar-coded electoral cards, voting ship with holograms, optical pen on a computer screen to facilitate vote counting system at the poll, the possibility of voting over the telephone or using magnetic cards or electronic communication through World Wide Web, all supported by the expanding use of computer science technologies (Lijphart *et al.*, 2007).

In Nigeria, elections have thwarted the effort of the people upon which democracy is built which is occasioned by election riggings that are evident in all the general elections. Peter and Inokoba (2023) averred that the adoption of technology has raised concerns and distrust for the electoral system in that the inability of electoral technologies to improve the outcomes of elections and facilitate democratic trust has generated a lot of questions such as: Is Nigeria ripe for electoral technology? Does Nigeria have the capacity to conduct credible elections despite the potential that electoral technology offers?

In Nigeria as in elsewhere, elections provide the platform for political succession. However, since political independence when electoral process continued to face constant abuse, the election platform now provide an opportunity for fraudulent individuals and groups to perpetrate acts of rigging against other contestants and the electorates. Through no fault of their own, stakeholders and the electorates are sidelined through unbridled rigging, thus losing the election or having their votes stolen or cancelled (Agbu, 2016). This was the situation until the arrival of the permanent voter's cards and the smart card reader in 2015. This technological input in Nigerian electoral space is supposed to make it extremely difficult for results to be manipulated, either by anonymous individuals or through arbitrarily and fraudulently manipulation of figures. Ordinarily, the transparent application of this electronic device and its embodied security features should make it extremely difficult to clone or compromise. This expectation has not been achieved as the politician's diverse different means that continued to compromise the integrity of electoral processes (Ogunmokun *et al.*, 2024).

Within 1999 and 2023, riggings during elections have witnessed a lot of bloodshed and many lives have been lost in what many stakeholders described as political killings normally executed by hired assassins from evil politicians who wanted to consolidate power and sustained it by any means. Some of the politicians in Nigeria imposed their electoral officers who go all out to ensure they win the election for their candidates against the will of the people. It can be described that elections conducted in Nigeria since attainment of political independence from the British have been played in a do or die affair thereby making many peace-loving Nigerians too scared to exercising their voting rights. The result is voters' apathy in most local, state and national elections conducted by the electoral bodies in Nigeria.

In the 2023 general elections, the electoral umpire introduced a technology device known as Bimodal Voters Authentication System (BVAS) and was determined to produce popular candidates that will win through majority of vote cast. Unfortunately, the greedy and corrupt politicians go every length to manipulate the process and the result what is that the outcome of the process was rejected by generality of Nigerians. The current economic crises have been blamed on bad leadership. The electoral officers help to

diverse means to rig the election to their preferred candidates who emerged as the winners. Evident has shown that the rate of citizen participation in elections these days have drastically reduced because many have been disappointed by the way and manner in which election have been conducted in Nigeria which is rather unfortunate.. This quest to win the election, by all means, has also claimed the lives of both the electorates and some popular candidates by some hoodlums who want to control the government by dubious means. Accordingly, those who have the interest of Nigerians at heart have resorted to shunning politics for fear of sudden death in the process and this has posed a serious threat to Nigerian democracy and its consolidation.

More worrisome is the fact that the electoral body who supposed to be neutral, and ensure free and fair elections have been biased because in some cases, they are employed by some power brokers to serve as a rescue mission to some of their illegitimate candidates against the will of the popular candidates to ensure that their unpopular candidates emerged victorious in elections, they have seen election rigging as a way out against the general wish of the people. Aborisade (2006) observed that rigging is almost synonymous with Nigerian elections. This ugly electoral malpractice and rigging have a negative effect on Nigeria's democratic future because the trend is increasing instead of reducing. These trends have actually undermined the chances of successful elections and the consolidation of democracy in Nigeria. Against the background, the study examined the effect of technological innovations on free, fair and credible election as fray electoral process pose danger to political instability in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Student

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of technological device, the biometric voters authentication system in Ethiope West Local Government, Delta State Nigeria, on election rigging and political instability in Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

- (a) To investigate the effect of biometry voters authentication system on credible election in Ethiope west local government.
- (b) To examine the impact of election rigging on credible election in Delta State.
- (c) To scrutinize the effect of fingerprint on credible election in Delta state Nigeria.
- (d) To determine the relationship between technology innovation and election credibility in Nigeria.
- (e) To appraise to what extent the introduction of BVAS has affected the people orientation on credible election in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

The literature review contained in this section consists of both conceptual, theoretical and empirical in line with extant studies as in Feddersen and Pesendorfer (1999) and most recently Blais (2000).

Conceptual Literature

The terms electoral technology and election technology are used interchangeably as they convey the same meaning. According to Bridgewater (2018), electoral technologies are technologies characterized by their input and output. They are viewed as black-boxed technologies because their implementations are usually not transparent, yet they are technologies deployed to simplify the complex and costly electoral process. All forms of technologies, usually diverse sets of hardware, software, ICT-related, electronics, digital, internet enabling, and other equipment, deployed by the election management bodies into each phase of the electoral cycle, to manage electoral activities and processes, in order to ensure a free and fair election, and the delivery of electoral services are conceptualized as electoral technologies (Haque & Carroll, 2020).

Winning elections in Nigeria is a serious business because it is a sure way of accessing state resources. As an aspiring democratic state, periodic free and fair elections are one of the pillars for sustaining democracy. Defined as a procedure that allows members of a state, organization or community to choose representatives who will hold positions of authority within it, and which promotes public accountability, elections are critical in ensuring participatory governance (Agbu, 2016). The concept of democracy is not

necessarily synonymous with elections; however, a free and fair election is generally accepted to be at the heart of democracy. A democratic government ideally denotes government composed through the freely given consent of the people as expressed in an election. Once the element of free consent is absent in an electoral process, then the outcome is no longer a democracy, but dictatorship (Aborisade 2006, p.115). Any election fraught with fraud and violence is therefore a usurpation of the sovereignty of the people, the equivalent of an electoral coup. Further, elections are one of the most important means of establishing legitimate government and exercising popular control over leaders. It is also a means of policy selection as set out in party manifestos during elections. An election is a process, and it is free if all stages of the process are devoid of inhibitions and contradictions. It is also fair if the process shows no favour to person, party or side. Fairness means acting in an honest and honourable manner that is in accordance with what is desirable according to rules (Okoh, 2005).

According to Peter and Inokoba (2023), election can be described as a pivotal mechanism through which citizens participate in their polity and democratic rule is delivered. Broadly, elections facilitate the transition or change of government that allows citizens to evaluate and chose their preferred candidates or party (Oriakhi, Chilaka &Oyinmiebi, 2019). On their part, Okoye and Oyinmiebi (2021) argue that a functional liberal democracy is judged by the type of election conducted. Hence, election is the benchmark for formalization of leadership recruitment and succession in democratic societies. it is for this reason that Okolie (2005) observes that “election confers legitimacy on public office holders and subject public office holders and political parties to periodic assessment and in doing so, it enhances accountability and good governance”. Therefore, until elections reinforce the values of democracy which allows for the transparency, choice, fairness, freedom, rule of law and due process; credibility remains lacking (Diamond, Okoye &Oyinmiebi, 2021).

The concept of electoral technology has been characterised by the use of different appellations to explain it. According to the MIT Election Data Science Lab (2023), electoral technology can be referred to as “voting technology”. Others have described electoral technology as “electronic voting” or “e-voting”, “ICT-driven elections”, “online voting”, “cyber elections” and so on (Garnett & James, 2020) view electronic voting as a system of voting in an election that involves the use of electronic methods for submitting and tallying votes. Electronic voting offers efficiency and cost-effectiveness in conducting voting, particularly when dealing with large amounts of data in real-time, while also emphasizing the need for robust security measures. This type of voting, eliminate the risks of fraud, irregularities and manipulations that may alter the outcome of the election.

According to Maurer (2020) electoral technology consist of digital solutions in solving the democratic challenges of conducting elections. Evidently, Maurer argued that electoral technology involves a broad range of “digital solutions” adopted in the electoral cycle, which covers registration, voting, collation and other activities. Digital solutions are already employed across different stages of the electoral cycle by various stakeholders such as election management bodies, voters, political parties, the media, and more. These solutions encompass technologies like geographic information systems, electronic registers and voting machines, optical scanners, e-transmission of results, electronic signatures for initiatives and candidate lists, result consolidation and visualization systems, and statistical methods for result evaluation and fraud detection. These digital solutions are based on digitized information.

Omoleke (2017) defines technology as more than just a tool or machine; he characterizes it as a multifaceted concept encompassing techniques and a cultural force. It extends beyond physical entities to include both material and immaterial creations resulting from the application of mental and physical efforts, all with the overarching goal of achieving certain values. In essence, technology goes beyond the tangible artefacts we commonly associate with the term and also involves the intangible aspects of knowledge, methodologies, and the cultural impact of innovation. This comprehensive definition highlights that technology is not solely confined to the physical tools or machinery but extends to the broader spectrum of techniques and the cultural influence embedded within these advancements. The term

encapsulates the entire process of ideation, creation, and implementation, acknowledging the mental and physical efforts invested in technological development. Moreover, he emphasizes the intrinsic connection between technology and values, suggesting that technological endeavours are driven by a pursuit of specific principles or goals (Layiwola, 2024).

Yakubu (2021) noted that election rigging can be defined as any process that has an illegal interference with the election process, either by increasing the votes of a particular candidate, suppressing the votes of a rival candidate, or both. He averred that no matter how little the magnitude of election rigging may be, it has adverse effects on the outcome of an election, because if the scale of rigging does not change the winner of the election, the confidence of the electorate in the electoral system is adversely affected. Election rigging can occur before, during or after an election is conducted. To consider the ways in which technology can be used to combat rigging, it is important to consider the acts involved in rigging which involve several multidimensional factors ranging from economic, social and political environment.

Theoretical Literature

Cybernetic Model of Communications Theory

The cybernetic model of communications theory is adopted by the study which was developed in the 1940s and was formulated by notable scholars such as Couffignal, and von Neumann Cybernetics, as defined by Nwangwu et al. (2018), pertains to the scientific examination of systems capable of receiving, storing, and processing information to utilize such data for control purposes. Comparable to David Easto's system analysis approach, the cybernetics model adopts an interdisciplinary perspective, aiming to elucidate the correlation between actions within a system and the resultant effect. In operation, the cybernetics model of communication encodes incoming information, recognizes patterns, stores these patterns in a memory unit, learns from experience, recalls information upon command, recombines information into new patterns, and applies stored information for problem-solving and decision-making (Oriaiki *et al.*, (2019).

This operational mechanism closely mirrors the functioning of electoral technologies, thus optimizing the election management system. This theoretical framework proves essential for comprehending the extent of technological deployment and the role technology assumes in the electoral process. Wiener (1969) submitted that the escalating complexity of the world necessitates the inevitable incorporation of technologies for administrative purposes. Election management aligns with this administrative imperative, resulting in the increasing global deployment of technology. The cybernetic model is therefore posited to enhance our understanding of the pursuit of credible elections through technological means, suggesting a positive correlation between the degree of technological deployment and the improved credibility of an election. However, Okoye and Oyinmiebi (2021) discern a limitation in the cybernetics model, contending that the involvement of human operators in handling and operating technologies leaves room for potential manipulations and human interference.

For instance, in Blais (2000), it was reported that a sense of duty plays an important role in the decision to vote for a large fraction of voters. He writes: I conclude that for many people voting is not only a right, it is also a duty. And the belief that in a democracy every citizen should feel obliged to vote which induces many people to vote in almost all elections. That sense of duty is not shared by everyone. It may vary from one country to another. It can also vary over time. There are a wide variety of formal models of turnout and the surveys mentioned above discuss the formal literature. The papers most closely related to our effort here are those by Morton (1991), Nalebuff and Shachar (1999). Altruism has been proposed as an explanation for anomalies (see, among others, (Monroe, 1994; Sugden, 1984). However, in models in which the marginal effect of a contribution decreases as total contributions increases, a "crowding out" effect is predicted. Thus, in a large population predicted contributions will be low. The crowding out effect is particularly severe in elections. If all voters prefer the same candidate then a single vote will crowd out all others. Hence, simple altruism cannot explain observed contribution patterns. Contributions

will be larger if, as assumed by Andreoni (1989), agents receive a “warm glow” payoff for contributing for the public good which is independent of the contribution of others.

As in the Riker and Ordeshook (1968) paper, the warm glow effect is exogenous. There is a warm glow aspect to our model. While we do not assume that agents receive a warm glow payoff for voting, agents do receive an additional payoff for doing their part. In a similar vein, Samuelson (1993) and Bergstrom (1995) among others, address the problem of how ethical preferences may arise as the consequence of evolutionary pressures. The crucial difference is that the optimal level of contributions for a public good may or may not be large whereas the social optimal level of turnout is necessarily small. This follows because in a large election, any result can be reproduced, at lower social cost, by taking a sufficiently representative sample.

Empirical Studies

Ogunmokun *et al.*, (2024) investigated the impact of electoral technologies on electoral system in Nigeria. The study was conducted in six offices of INEC across the south west geopolitical zone made of Lagos, Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti states as well as INEC national office in Abuja. A sample of 240 questionnaire was utilized by the study which focused on the impact of electoral technologies on the electoral system in Nigeria. The study employed binary logistic regression model and findings indicated evidence of significant positive effect of electoral technologies on electoral system in Nigeria. The study recommended continuous improvement in the use of electoral technologies by the electoral body.

Ayeni and Esan (2018) assessed the effect of ICT on the conduct of election in Nigeria covering the period, 1999 general elections to 2017. The study found that the introduction of these technologies which include Electronic Voters Register (EVR), Automatic Fingerprints Identification System (AFIS) and Smart Card Reader (SCR) have reduced the incidence of multiple registration and multiple voting to the barest minimum while the development of e-collation support platform has drastically reduced incidence of result manipulation at collation centres. The study concluded that the incorporation of Information and Communication Technology in Nigeria electoral process has reduced excessive electoral fraud to the barest minimum and foster credible elections.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed survey research design method for the purpose of collecting data and adopted the cross-sectional technique data gathering from respondents. The population of the study covered 2,105 population across ETHIOPE WEST in Delta State. The sample size was determined by using Babalola (2003) determination Table. To make up this subset, the approximate number 200 sample size was selected from the total population. A primary source of data through questionnaire was relied upon. The details needed from respondents include age, marital status, educational level, gender. This was followed by questions. A five (5) point Likert-scale was used for the assessment of the opinions of the respondents as provided (Eguavoen, 2009). In what followed, measurement of the model reliability was evaluated using Cronbach’s alpha-based tests. Cronbach’s alpha provides an estimate of the indicator and correlations. An acceptable measure for Cronbach’s alpha is 0.8 or higher, while below 0.8 connoted weak reliability (Adebisi, 2015).

4. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents.

Demographic information	Frequency	Percent
Female	200	100%
Age		
22-29	87	43.5%
30-37	54	27%
37-43	33	16.5%
44+	26	13%
Religion		
Christianity	120	60%
Muslim	56	28%
Others	24	12%
Marital Status		
Single	33	16.5%
Married	160	80%
Divorced/Separated	07	3.5%
Educational Level		
Primary	47	23.5%
Secondary	98	49%
Tertiary	55	27.5%
Ethnicity		
Itsekiri or Ijaw	73	36.5%
Igbo	62	31%
Yoruba	41	20.5%
Hausa	18	9%
Fulani	06	3%

The following findings were reached by the study: The deployment of technology for voter registration is seen as a factor boosting the acceptability of election outcomes, as people can now access and verify the voters' register. Likewise, the transparency provided by technology, such as the BVAS, has increased people's confidence in the electoral system and its outcomes. Overall, the use of technology is seen as a positive force in building trust and confidence in the electoral processes in Nigeria. However, the study found that despite the deployment of BVAS, underaged voting and over voting were very prominent most especially in the northern part of Nigeria in the 2023 general elections leading to disaffections among contestants.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study assessed the relationship between technological innovations and free, fair and credible elections in Nigeria using data from two local government areas in Delta State. The study noted that the use of the technological devices such as permanent voters' cards and BVAS were designed to eliminate malpractices and election rigging and add to the credibility of the elections. To some extent this expectation was attained but noted that several drawbacks were observed during the 2023 general elections.

The study further observed that elections are credible when they are premised on a quantitative and qualitative national register of votes. Similarly, elections conducted on the basis of the foregoing become credible if they meet popular participation while citizens and ballot safety are securitized. However, election security remains paramount in Nigeria for the safety of personnel and the election process and which must be taken seriously. The 2023 general elections were saddled with cases of malfeasance notable among which was underaged voting despite the fact that BVAS technology was used for the

elections. This made people to express mixed feelings on the deployment of electoral technology to address the several election related challenges. The study used primary data sourced through questionnaires and employed logistic regression. Findings indicated that although the technology stirred people interest in the electoral process but found that cases of underaged voting affected the credibility of the 2023 general elections.

The study concluded that the introduction of technology devices in the electoral process do not seem to help matter as complaints of weak internet and broadband connectivity hindered the smooth functioning of electoral technology thereby limiting its effectiveness in facilitating elections. Notably, the weak cybersecurity infrastructure in Nigeria has left the electoral system vulnerable to hacking, raising concerns about the integrity and security of the electoral process. Furthermore, the logistical preparedness to address electoral bodies has been a concern resulting in inadequate planning and implementation that affect the successful deployment of technology. Lastly, a significant trust deficit in the electoral system exacerbated by the election management bodies and the ruling political class hampered the acceptance and trust in electoral technology. It is therefore recommended that the technological device to block loopholes that negate credible elections and culture of impunities in electoral system must be uphold in Nigeria.

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